

Anti-British Uprising in Assam : A Historical Study (1826-1857)

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Abstract:

The anti-British uprising in Assam formed an important chapter in the history of resistance against colonial rule in India. After the British annexed Assam following the treaty of Yandaboo (1826) various sections of Assamese society- including peasants, tribal communities, nobles, religious leaders and freedom fighters opposed British political domination, economic exploitation and cultural interference. These uprising reflected both local grievances and broader nationalist sentiment. From the revolts of Assamese nobles to tribal insurgencies and peasant protests, the people of Assam demonstrated courage and determination in defending their political rights, economic interests and cultural identity. The anti-British uprising creates the political consciousness in Assam. Realizing the importance of the topic it is intended to formulate a brief description on the subject within its very limit. The whole process of the preparation of this paper is to be completed by applying historical method of study.

Keywords: Assamese, society, economic freedom, nobles, uprising.

1. Introduction:

In 1228 AD. The Ahom came in to Assam and established Ahom kingdom known as 'Asom' or Assam. The Ahom ruled Assam from 1228 to 1826 AD. About 600 years. The established a strong and powerful administration and gave peace, prosperity and happiness to Assamese population. Under the Ahom administration brought various tribes and neighbouring territories and its led to the political unity of Assam.

The treaty of Yandaboo 1826 was the turning point of in the history of Assam. It ended the six hundred years of old Ahom rule in Assam. British annexed Assam in stages,

beginning in 1826 after defeating the Burmese in the first Anglo-Burmese War. This expansion transformed the region's political, economic and social structure. In 1838 the upper Assam and the rest of the Ahom territories were formally annexed into the British Empire in 1826 for administration convenience the British divided of Assam into two parts upper Assam and lower Assam. David Scott, the agent to the governor general for North Eastern Frontier had now appointed the senior commissioner of lower Assam and Guwahati as his headquarter. On the otherhand Col Richard had appointed the Jr. Commissioner of upper Assam with his headquarter at Rangpur.

2. Objectives of the Study:

This paper proposes to study the following objectives-

- i) To study the political conditions of Assam on the eve of the British.
- ii) To find out the socio-economic conditions of the time.
- iii) To find out the circumstances leading to the annexation of Assam.
- iv) To find out the causes and effects of Anti-British uprisings.

3. Methodology:

The topic of the identified paper directly related with historical events and the relevant data would be found only historical literature. In those circumstances this paper will be completed by adopting historical method of study. The relevant data will be collected from the historical books published by reliable published and authors and also from the reliable web pages published in various websites. For instance this paper will be completed only using the secondary data.

4. Analysis:

The whole paper will be discusses on the following heads-

Welcome to the British:

In 1826 the British had established their Regime almost overall India. In the last part, their territory was increased to Goalpara which had the common border with the Assam. So, it is clear that Assam was also come under their colonies. At first Assamese people including the ruling classes welcome the British because they defeated the Burmese, who destroyed

more than half of the Assamese population. At first the Ahom princes and nobles of the Ahom court believed that the British would not occupy Assam permanently and restoration of Ahom Raj, they will go back. But they did not do the same and they occupied the whole area of Ahom kingdom.

The introduction of British rule was not viewed with favour by a section of population of Assam. They remained discontent. But the feelings of discontentment were continued only to the Assamese nobility and members of the Ahom royal family. Their discontentment soon found in the expression of a series of unsuccessful attempts to through off alien rules, which were as follows-

4.1 Rebellion of Gomdhar Konwar:

The rebellion of Gomdhar Konwar against the East India Company was the first resistance movement of Assamese people against the alien rule. He was the son of a prince of Ahom royal family Phena Konwar. It was the first reaction to the new administrative measures of company Government. But the revolt was poor organized and suppressed a detachment of troops under Lt. Rutherford in Oct. 1828. All though this rebellion of Gomdhar Konwar suppressed by the British, yet it inspired the others to fight against the foreign rulers.

4.2 Rebellion of Gadadhar Singha, 1829:

The revolt of Gadadhar Singha, a prince of Ahom royal family was very important. Gadadhar Singha was the son of Dhutura Gohain and was closely related to the Ahom king Chandra Kanta Singha. He revolted against the British. But he was arrested by the British police force and sent to Gauhati for trail of his conspiracy. Though the rebellion of Gadadhar Singha failed yet in instigated the future generation for another rebellion against the British rule in Assam.

4.3 Revolt of Upper Assam, 1830:

In 1830 a group of nobles led by Pealia Borgohain allies Dhanjoy revolted against the British Pealia Borgohain was the central figure in the rebellion of Gomdhar Konwar. Jeuram Dihingia Barua, Haranath Rupchand Konwar and Singpho. It was the last organized rebellion against the alien rule led by the noble classes in Assam. The rebels had collected a force of huge armed men planned to march towards Rangpur and to attack the town after killing the

security force. They address letters to the tribal chief of Naga, Khamti, Mayamaria, Khasi, Garo etc. for help than with arms. It was buddy failed in their endeavor mainly due to their ill fortune rather than miss management. Though this rebellion had failed yet, it instigated for the future generation for rebellion against the British.

4.4 The Revolt of 1857:

The year of 1857 was eventful year in the history of India. The revolt 1857 was a great challenge before the British ruler. In Assam Maniram Dewan was the fountainhead of revolt of 1857. At first Maniram was the reliable person of the company Government. He prepared of revolt against the British were completed by Sept/1857 But unlucky before declaration of the Revolt Maniram Dewan was arrested. Maniram Dewan and Piyali Barua were tired on Feb/23rd 1857 and convicted to treason. Maniram and Pyali Barua publicly hanged at Jorhat on Feb.1857. Thus other leaders were given sentences to imprisonment.

It is seen that in spite of the political and organizational success of Maniram and his associates, they failed to cause an outbreak comparable to those creating commotions in other parts of India. This failure mainly due to the fact that the rebels were both small in number and isolated and also that they lacked military leadership of any distinction.

4.5 Revolt of Neighbouring Hills Tribe:

Thus the tribal people of neighbouring hill tribes of Assam rebelled against the British. The Khasi chiefs of neighbouring hills also opposed British expansion in Assam. U.Tirat Sing led armed resistance against the British between 1829 and 1833. Due to threat of Khasi independence and British attempts to build roads through Khasi territory they opposed British expansion in the hilly area.

The Singpho and Khamti tribes of upper Assam also revolted against British authority during 1830. The Khamtis attacked the British garrison at Sadiya and killed several British officers. The British later suppressed the revolt with military force.

The British Government was successful to suppress all these uprising through their planned policy and they consolidated their position. But it is assumed that though the British Government was temporarily successful to suppress the uprising, but these uprising paved the way for future movement of Indian independence.

Conclusion:

Anti-British uprising in Assam during the period 1826 to 1857 AD. is a very important event in the history of Assam. The British established their administration in Assam in 1826 as a result of the treaty of Yandaboo (1826) the introduction of the British rule was not viewed with favour by a sanction of the population of Assam.

They remained discontent. Their discontentment soon found in the expansion of a series of unsuccessful attempts t through these alien rule. It is unfortunate that these no any systematic attempts has been made to highlight the events of the Ant-British in Assam before the present generations.

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